

1 **Assessing the electrochemical performance of different phenazines as**
2 **cathodes for Zn-ion batteries**

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22

23 **Abstract**

24

25 The constant growth in energy demand to meet society's needs is placing increasing strain
26 on natural resources. To mitigate this issue, organic battery cathodes based on
27 biomolecules derived from the metabolism of microorganisms might provide a
28 sustainable alternative to inorganic compounds. In this work, four phenazine compounds
29 (phenazine - PZ, Phenazine-1-carboxylic acid – PCA, Phenazin-1-ol – POH, and
30 Phenazine-1-carboxamide – PCN), with PCA being synthesized by recombinant
31 *Escherichia coli* cell, were assessed as cathodes for aqueous Zn-ion batteries (ZIB). All
32 cathodes exhibited stable specific capacity ($> 100 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$) during 1,000 cycles at 1 A
33 g^{-1} without dissolution. As suggested after Density Function Theory (DFT) analysis, the
34 lower specific capacity observed for PCA is attributed to the strong interaction of Zn^{2+}
35 ions and the carboxylic group. Overall, DFT correctly predicted the influence of distinct
36 ligands on the oxidation and reduction peaks of substituted phenazines. *Ex situ* Fourier
37 Transform Infrared (FTIR) measurements yielded notable results regarding solid
38 electrolyte formation in the presence of Zinc trifluoromethanesulfonate ($\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$). The
39 $\text{Zn}^{2+}/\text{H}^+$ ion pairing might occur simultaneously to counterbalance charge on phenazines;
40 however, local alkalization during discharge, revealed with POH as new *in situ* acid-
41 base indicator, is detrimental for Zn^{2+} ions resulting in their precipitation, especially in
42 the presence of $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$. In contrast, when ZnSO_4 was used as the electrolyte,
43 precipitation induced by local alkalization seemed to not affect the performance of
44 phenazines.

45

46 **Keywords:** Phenazine; organic cathode; energy storage; conversion reaction, Zn-ion
47 battery; biosynthesis.

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49

50 1. Introduction

51

52 The global demand for energy storage is continuously increasing as our society
53 delves deeper into the fourth industrial revolution, driven by digital and information
54 technology [1]. This surge is amplifying the need for mobile applications, ranging from
55 electrical vehicles and service robots [2] to tools and portable devices. Such a scenario
56 places immense pressure on the current capacity of industries to supply Li-ion batteries
57 to meet global demand [1,3,4], raising concerns about the abundance of minerals [5], their
58 extraction and refining processes, and the associated environmental impacts [6], including
59 that of spent batteries [7].

60 As global demand for energy storage devices continues to rise, researchers are
61 exploring new materials to compete with and/or replace Li-ion batteries. Given the
62 scarcity of lithium and the pressing need for more sustainable solutions [8,9], alternative
63 storage materials, such as Zn-ion batteries, that now focus on organic compounds as
64 cathodes [10–13]. These compounds, typically composed of carbon, hydrogen, oxygen,
65 nitrogen, and sulfur, are abundant, environmentally friendly, sustainable, low-cost, and
66 can be synthesized through chemical and biological processes [12,14], including from
67 sources derived from biomass [15,16].

68 Phenazine-based compounds present an intriguing option as natural products of
69 the secondary metabolism in certain classes of microorganisms, particularly those in the
70 genera *Pseudomonas* and *Streptomyces*. These nitrogenous aromatic compounds,
71 featuring simple substituent groups such as hydroxyls and carboxyls, hold significant
72 potential for biotechnological applications in agriculture, pharmacy, fuels, and energy
73 storage [17]. Wang et al. [18] used phenazine (PZ) and 2,3-diamine-phenazine (DAP) as
74 cathodes for Zn-ion battery. A high specific capacity (232 mA h g^{-1} at 20 mA g^{-1}) was
75 achieved using PZ, with no dissolution into the electrolyte. *Ex situ* Fourier Transform
76 Infrared (FTIR) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses indicated that C=N
77 bonds facilitated Zn^{2+} ion pairing. However, for DAP, the presence of hydrophilic groups
78 caused it to easily dissolve in the ZnSO_4 electrolyte. Li et al. [19] prepared a composite
79 of PZ and Ketjen carbon black as an interesting strategy to prevent dissolution and
80 achieve a long-term cycle stability. Vallayil *et al.* [20] showed that using commercial
81 NafionTM as a binder significantly improved both stability and specific capacity of
82 phenazine as active material.

83 While an aqueous electrolyte offers advantages in terms of cost and safety for the
84 battery, it also limits the electrochemical window and restricts the choice of metals for
85 the anode, as sodium and lithium are only suitable for batteries with organic solvents. In
86 this context, zinc appears as a potential candidate for this type of system, as in addition
87 to being able to be used in aqueous rechargeable batteries, it has additional advantages of
88 its natural availability, high stability and high volumetric energy density [21]. The issues
89 regarding parasitic reactions of H₂ evolution and dendrite formation can be bypassed
90 using innovative strategies [22–24].

91 In the present study, we aim to assess and compare four phenazine compounds,
92 each with distinct substituent groups, after selecting an appropriate current collector to
93 prevent dissolution as active material for ZIB. The compounds investigated include
94 phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), phenazine-1-ol (POH), and
95 phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) – see Table S1 for the chemical structures. A series of
96 electrochemical experiments, including chronopotentiometry, electrochemical
97 impedance, and galvanostatic intermittent titration, were conducted to comprehensively
98 characterize the oxidation/reduction potential, charge retention, specific capacity, and
99 energy and power density of the phenazines. Additionally, theoretical predictions for the
100 most stable positions of phenazines with and without Zn²⁺ ions and their vibrational
101 spectrum, and experimental analyses, including *ex situ* FTIR, XPS, and scanning electron
102 microscopy coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, were performed to
103 elucidate the Zn²⁺ ion pairing mechanism using ZnSO₄ and Zinc
104 trifluoromethanesulfonate (Zn(OTf)₂) as electrolyte. Finally, the Zn anode was
105 electrochemically assessed within the supporting electrolytes used.

106

107 **2. Materials and methods**

108

109 **2.1 Chemical reagents**

110 Chemical reagents, including Phenazine (PZ, a.r., Tokyo Chemical Industry),
111 Phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA, biologically prepared – see Text S1 – and its standard
112 from Cayman Chemical, commercialized as Tubercmycin B), phenazine-1-ol (POH, a.r.,
113 Tokyo Chemical Industry), Phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN, a.r. Tokyo Chemical
114 Industry), Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF, a.r., Sigma-Aldrich), Ketjen carbon black
115 (KCB: Nouryon), XC72 (Cabot), Black Pearl 2000 (BP: Cabot), N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone
116 (NMP: a.r., Sigma-Aldrich), CDCl₃ (a.r., Sigma-Aldrich), Zn foil (99.95% purity, Sigma

117 Aldrich), ZnSO₄ (a.r., Synth), Zn(OTf)₂ (Zinc trifluoromethanesulfonate, a. r., Ambeed),
118 PVA (Polyvinylalcohol, a.r., available as Mowiol® 18-88, Sigma Aldrich), KBr (infrared
119 grade, Sigma Aldrich) were used as received without prior treatment. All solutions were
120 prepared using deionized water (Millipore Milli-Q Direct-Q® 5 UV system, $\rho \geq 18.2$ M Ω
121 cm). ¹H Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (HNMR) data for PZ, PCA (standard and
122 biologically synthesized), POH, and PCN can be seen in Fig. S1 and Text S2.

123

124 **2.2 Electrode preparation and electrochemical tests**

125 Initially, PZ (or its derivatives, such as PCA, POH, PCN – 65% *m/m*) and KCB
126 (20% *m/m*) were weighed and macerated in an agate mortar. Then, these solids were
127 transferred to a glass tube containing the PVDF solution in NMP (15% *m/m*), previously
128 weighed. To this mixture, 1050 μ L of NMP (70% *V/V*) were added, to facilitate the
129 dispersion of the solid, and kept under stirring with a magnetic bar for 20 min. Then, 450
130 μ L of ultrapure water (corresponding to 30% *V/V*) were added. The resulting dispersion
131 was left for 24 h under constant magnetic stirring at 800 rpm. After this period, the
132 solution was dripped onto flexible graphite substrates (10 mm in diameter and 1 mm
133 thick), previously weighed. Immediately after dripping, the electrodes were taken and left
134 in an oven at 60 °C for 24 h to evaporate the solvent. Finally, the electrodes were
135 reweighed and used to assemble the Swagelok-type electrochemical cell with 2 or 3
136 electrodes. The choice of KCB and flexible graphite substrate as additive and current
137 collector, respectively, were based on previous investigations, as described below.

138 The two-electrode setup consisted of the positive electrode (previously described),
139 a Zn foil (0.25 mm thick and 10 mm in diameter) as negative electrode, and two glass
140 fiber membranes (12 mm in diameter, Whatman™), as separator. To the latter, 110 μ L of
141 a 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ solution were dropped. For the electrochemical impedance tests, an
142 Ag/AgCl/KCl (3 mol L⁻¹) reference electrode was also used.

143 Electrochemical tests were carried out in the potential range from 0.3 V to 1.4 V
144 vs. Zn/Zn²⁺, including: *i*) electrochemical impedance (EI: ± 10 mV from 15 kHz to 0.5
145 mHz) with respect to open circuit conditions (after 3600 s of resting), *ii*) cyclic
146 voltammetry at different scan rates (0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 and 1 mV s⁻¹), *iii*) galvanostatic
147 intermittent titration (GITT) that consisted of applying mass densities of current of 400
148 mA g⁻¹ for 60 s, followed by a period (100 s) without current application [25], *iv*)
149 galvanostatic charge and discharge (GCD) measurements at different mass current
150 densities (200, 400, 800, 1000, 2000 and 4000 mA g⁻¹), *v*) shelf test

151 (chronopotentiometric measurements applying 800 mA g⁻¹ with an interval of 24 h
 152 between charging and discharging), and vi) GCD measurements using 1000 mA g⁻¹ for
 153 1000 cycles. For the latter test, a 2 mol L⁻¹ Zn(OTf)₂ electrolyte was also assessed.

154 The specific capacity (C / mA h g⁻¹), average specific energy density (E_S / W h
 155 kg⁻¹), and average specific power density (P_S / W kg⁻¹) were calculated according to:

$$157 \quad C = \frac{I \times t}{m} \quad (1)$$

$$158 \quad E_S = C \times E \quad (2)$$

$$161 \quad P = \frac{I \times E}{m} \quad (3)$$

162

163 where I is the applied electric current (A), t the discharge time (h), m the mass of active
 164 material (kg), E the average cell voltage during discharge.

165 To evaluate the electrochemical performance of a Zn/Zn symmetrical cell, cyclic
 166 voltammetry (10 mV s⁻¹), linear sweep polarization (1 mV s⁻¹), and a prolonged stripping
 167 and plate experiment (0.5 mA cm⁻² for 3600 s during oxidation and reduction steps) were
 168 also carried using ZnSO₄ and Zn(OTf)₂ at 2 mol L⁻¹ as well as 1 mol L⁻¹ Zn(OTf)₂
 169 dissolved in 50 g L⁻¹ PVA as electrolytes (Zn(OTf)₂/PVA).

170

171 **2.3 Surface characterization after charge and discharge cycles**

172 Field emission scanning electron (FEG, Philips XL30) micrographs coupled to
 173 energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy analyses were carried out in samples after a
 174 complete charge (1.4 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺) and discharge (0.3 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺) to assess the
 175 resulting morphology of the working electrode. Before such experiments, samples were
 176 thoroughly rinsed with ultrapure water and dried in a vacuum oven at ambient
 177 temperature.

178 The surface elemental analysis of phenazine and its derivatives was performed by
 179 *ex situ* X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using a commercial spectrometer K-
 180 alpha XPS (Thermo Scientific) after a complete charge (1.4 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺) and discharge
 181 (0.3 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺). The Al K α line ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) was used as the ionization source
 182 and the pass energy of the analyzer was set to 50 eV for the high-resolution spectra. Other
 183 parameters kept constant were spot size (300 μ m), step size (0.10 eV), dwell time (50

184 ms), and number of scans (10). The inelastic background of the C 1s, O 1s, N 1s and Zn
185 2p_{3/2} high-resolution spectra was subtracted using the Shirley method. The deconvolution
186 of the experimental spectra was performed using a Voigtian type function, with Gaussian
187 (70%) and Lorentzian (30%) combinations. The width at half height varied between 1.0
188 and 2.0 eV and the position of the peaks was determined with an accuracy of ± 0.1 eV
189 with respect to the hydrocarbon peak located at 294.9 eV.

190 *Ex situ* Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements were used
191 to characterize surface functional groups after a complete charge (1.4 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺) and
192 discharge (0.3 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺) using 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ and, comparatively, using Zn(OTf)₂.
193 For such, the mass composition of the working electrode was changed to phenazine and
194 its derivatives (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB. After
195 each electrochemical cycle, the electrode was thoroughly rinsed with ultrapure water and
196 dried in a vacuum oven at ambient temperature. Then, the film was carefully removed
197 from the current collector and the resulting powder was mixed with KBr (*ca.* 1:150 *m/m*).
198 After being macerated in an agata mortar, the powder was pressed into a pellet (10 mm
199 in diameter) for analysis using the IR-Prestige 21 spectrometer (Shimadzu), operating
200 from 4200 to 240 cm⁻¹.

201 *Ex situ* ¹H Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (HNMR) analysis of PZ at distinct
202 operating voltages was carried out using a Bruker Advance III-400 equipment, operating
203 at 9.4 T magnetic field (400 MHz for ¹H). As previously described for *ex situ* FTIR
204 measurements, each electrode sample was analyzed after interruption of the
205 chronopotentiometric assay in the second cycle at 1.4, 0.75, 0.55, and 0.3 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺
206 using 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄. Then, the electrode (with KCB and PVDF at 20% and 15%,
207 respectively) was thoroughly rinsed with ultrapure water and dried in a vacuum oven at
208 an ambient temperature. Subsequently, the film was removed from the current collector
209 and dissolved in CDCl₃ before NMR.

210

211 **2.4 Theoretical calculations**

212 Quantum calculations were performed using density functional theory (DFT) with
213 the B3-LYP hybrid functional, which combines Becke's gradient-corrected exchange-
214 correlation with the Lee-Yang-Parr correlation functional, incorporating three parameters
215 [26]. Dispersion corrections (DFT-D4) [27] were included, and calculations used TZVPP
216 atomic basis sets [28] within the TURBOMOLE software package [29]. Molecular
217 geometry optimizations were carried out without imposing symmetry constraints. The

218 convergence criteria for optimization required a change in total energy of 10^{-6} atomic
219 units (au) and a maximum geometric gradient norm of 10^{-3} au. For DFT calculations,
220 numerical integration used a grid step of 10^{-7} au to ensure high accuracy in energies and
221 geometries of the phenazine molecule and its derivatives, both with and without Zn^{2+} ,
222 identifying the most stable positions. The vibrational spectrum for all isolated systems
223 was also determined.

224

225 **3. Results and discussion**

226

227 **3.1 Electrochemical performance of Zn-ion battery using different phenazines**

228 Exploratory measurements were performed to test the carbon supports and current
229 collectors. Fig. S2a shows cyclic voltammetry and chronopotentiometric measurements
230 of phenazine as the active material in the presence of distinct carbon black additives, *i.e.*,
231 KCB, XC72 and BP. As shown in that figure, KCB exhibited well-defined oxidation and
232 reduction peaks, superior specific capacity across varying mass current densities (except
233 at 200 mA g^{-1}), and good specific capacity retention (Fig. S2b). The use of XC72 caused
234 a reduction in specific capacity. The performance of distinct current collectors, such as
235 flexible graphite, carbon paper (AvCarbonP50 and MGL 280), and a graphite rod was
236 carried out during GCD measurements at different mass current densities, as shown in
237 Fig. S3. The use of carbon paper or graphite rod resulted in a continuous decrease in the
238 specific capacity during the experiment, especially in the first cycles. On the other hand,
239 flexible graphite exhibited a significant stability over 1000 cycles at 1 A g^{-1} , with a low
240 dispersion between repetitions. Thus, the remaining experiments were carried out using
241 KCB and flexible graphite.

242 Initially, cyclic voltammetry tests were carried out at different scan rates and using
243 PZ, PCA, POH, and PCN as active material. Fig. 1 shows the CV curves at 0.1 mV s^{-1}
244 (2nd cycle) for a better definition of the oxidation and reduction peaks of PZ and its
245 derivatives, whose values underwent a shift depending on the substituent (see Table 1).
246 PCA exhibited peaks with highest oxidation and reduction potential; however, the mass
247 current densities were lower than PZ, POH, and PCN. The grey capacitive area refers to
248 the contribution of the KCB as the sole active material (85% *m/m* and PVDF 15% *m/m*).
249 Clearly, organic compounds are active and show distinct electrochemical behavior. The
250 relationship between scan rate and mass current density were assessed according to eq. 4
251

$$j = av^x \quad (4)$$

253

254 where j is the obtained mass current density, a is a proportionality constant, v is the scan
255 rate, and x expresses the degree of dependence of the current density on the scan rate.
256 Thus, x values close to 0.5 are indicative of a battery, whereas values close to 1 are
257 characteristic of a supercapacitor. As shown in Table 1, the x values for all prepared
258 electrodes (considering values at the oxidation and reduction peaks) remained
259 approximately at the expected value of 0.5. To gain further insight into how the
260 substituents of PZ affect the oxidation and reduction potential observed in the CV
261 measurements, analyses of the HOMO and LUMO theoretical values are essential, as can
262 be seen in Table 2. The -OH group, being an electron-donating group (due to lone pairs
263 on the oxygen atom participating in resonance with the aromatic ring), results in the
264 HOMO of POH (-5.98 eV) being higher than that of PZ (-6.31 eV). This indicates that
265 POH is slightly easier to oxidize than PZ, as seen in Fig.1 and Table 1. In terms of the
266 LUMO, POH has a lower value (-2.75 eV) compared to PZ (-2.67 eV), making POH
267 easier to reduce. The lower potential observed in the CV curve might be attributed to the
268 enhanced solvation of the generated POH anions. Considering that the -COOH and -
269 CONH₂ substituents of PCA and PCN, respectively, are electron-withdrawing group, the
270 HOMO of PCA (-6.86 eV) and PCN (-6.59 eV) are lower than that of PZ, indicating that
271 PCA and PCN are harder to oxidize than PZ, consistent with the CV curves. Conversely,
272 the estimated LUMO values of PCA (-3.35 eV) and PCN (-3.06 eV) are lower than that
273 of PZ, which indicates an easier reduction process (higher reduction potential). The
274 HOMO-LUMO gap of substituted phenazines was slightly lower than that of PZ,
275 suggesting that these compounds may exhibit improved conductivity. After pairing Zn²⁺
276 ion (see discussion below), the HOMO, LUMO, and Fermi levels decreased further,
277 suggesting that high electronic stability was achieved.

278 To investigate the performance of substituted phenazines against different mass
279 current densities, GCD tests were conducted, as illustrated in Fig. 2 (see the charge and
280 discharge profiles in Fig. S4). As expected, increasing the applied mass current density
281 caused a gradual decrease in the specific capacity values for all tested active materials,
282 approaching the behavior of the electrode prepared with KCB (pure capacitive behavior).
283 It is noteworthy that PCN exhibited the highest specific capacity values, followed by
284 POH, PZ, and PCA. For all cathodes, the specific capacity was recovered when the GCD
285 assay returned to 200 mA g⁻¹. Furthermore, no evidence of dissolution or oxidation of the

286 active material was under any of the tested mass current density conditions, which would
287 otherwise have resulted in a decrease in specific capacity. To gain further evidence on the
288 stability of PZ, *ex situ* ^1H NMR spectra exhibited no changes in the range of 1.4 to 0.3 V
289 (see Fig. S5).

290 The shelf test of the organic compounds can be seen in Fig. S6. After the initial
291 charge, the cell potential dropped to distinct values remaining at *ca.* 1.2 V (PCN and
292 POH), 1.1 V (PZ), and below 1.0 V *vs.* Zn/Zn^{2+} for PCA. The higher potential retention
293 by POH and PCN suggested greater conductivity (low HOMO-LUMO gap, see Table 2)
294 than PZ, which in turn is more conductive than PCA. For the latter, there was a sharp
295 potential drop, with recovery observed after 24 h of OCP. After the resting time, cell
296 discharge was performed, showing no significant variation in specific capacities
297 compared to previous GCD tests, with energy efficiencies consistently close to 100%. For
298 the KCB electrode, a rapid charge and discharge (after OCP) process was observed, which
299 is characteristic of typical capacitor behavior.

300 The temporal stability and charge retention of the different substituted phenazines
301 were assessed by prolonged GCD at 1 A g^{-1} for 1,000 cycles. Prior to these tests, the
302 active material was analyzed by EI and activated through CV (5 cycles at 0.5 mV s^{-1}). As
303 shown in Fig. 3a, all tested active materials (in duplicate) exhibited remarkable stability
304 in specific capacity values when using ZnSO_4 (see Fig. S7 for the similar values of the
305 specific energy density and power density of the assessed compounds and comparison
306 with selected works). This indicates that the active materials did not undergo dissolution
307 or degradation, further confirmed by the absence of a yellowish color on the glass
308 membrane after the experiment was interrupted. Notably, the faradaic efficiency
309 remained at 100% in all measurements (not shown). For the prolonged tests, the best
310 performances were observed in the sequence of POH, PCN, PZ, and PCA. For
311 comparison purposes, similar GCD tests (1 A g^{-1} for 1,000 cycles) were carried out using
312 $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ as electrolyte (see Fig. 3b). The analysis of that figure shows that all specific
313 capacity values of phenazines seemed to converge (specific capacity of PCA increased
314 and for POH decreased – *ca.* 100% of faradaic efficiency for all compounds), in contrast
315 to what was observed when using ZnSO_4 as electrolyte. In addition, PZ and POH
316 exhibited a slow decrease of the specific capacity values during cycles. That behavior
317 might be due to surface film formation, discussed below.

318 Based on the results obtained from the EI measurements, no significant variation
319 in charge transfer resistances was observed for the different organic compounds tested.

320 This is evident from the two semicircles at high and medium frequencies in the complex
321 plane of Fig. S8a (see also the similar total impedance of Fig. S8b). The main difference
322 among the compounds was noted in the lower frequency region, which is indicative of
323 diffusion processes involving Zn^{2+} ions. For the PCA compound, the lower slope
324 observed may be associated with a higher diffusion coefficient of Zn^{2+} ions (see the
325 discussion below using the GITT and DFT theoretical values).

326

327 **3.2 Examining the positive electrode reactions: the role of Zn^{2+} and H^+ ions**

328 Considering previous studies on using organic compounds as cathode for ZIB in
329 aqueous media, the contributions of H^+ and the effect of local pH effect during cycling
330 cannot be disregarded. Initially, GITT tests were performed, as shown in Fig. S9a (see
331 also Fig. S10 for the discharge step profile). The calculated electrochemical diffusion
332 coefficient (\tilde{D}) for the active materials exhibited similar behavior: an initial drop (*ca.* 0.1
333 $\leq x \leq 0.3$), followed by a slight rise and gradual decline. This pattern may indicate initial
334 charge pairing/conversion involving H^+ ions (high \tilde{D} values at high voltages) succeeded
335 by Zn^{2+} ions (low \tilde{D} at low voltages, as local pH tends to increase during discharge (see
336 discussion below). Lin *et al.* [30] also observed the co-insertion of H^+ and Zn^{2+} ions when
337 using a covalent organic framework produced from the condensation reaction between
338 tetraamino-p-benzoquinone and benzoquinone. Sun *et al.* [31] reported a similar result
339 regarding the co-insertion of H^+ and Zn^{2+} ions when using electrodeposited MnO_2 as the
340 cathode. This behavior was related to higher charge transfer and diffusion resistances, as
341 well as increased overvoltage below 1.0 V (*vs.* Zn/Zn^{2+}). For the PCN compound, an
342 interesting behavior was observed, with the fraction of Zn^{2+} ions incorporated (x values)
343 exceeding 1 (Fig. S9a), suggesting a reaction involving the carboxamide group; however,
344 no further studies were conducted. All \tilde{D} values remained consistent across the tested
345 organic compounds and exhibited a continuous decrease due to electrostatic repulsion.
346 Similar experiments were conducted using distinct carbon black materials with PZ as the
347 active material, as shown in Fig. S9b. For the XC72 compound, unlike previous behavior,
348 a continuous decrease in \tilde{D} values was observed.

349 To assess the potential influence of H^+ ions on the conversion reaction, CV tests
350 were carried out under two different pH conditions, *i.e.* 4.5 (natural pH of the ZnSO_4
351 solution 2 mol L^{-1}) and 2.4 (acidified with 0.5 mol L^{-1} of H_2SO_4). According to the Nernst
352 equation, a potential shift of *ca.* 0.1 V was expected when varying electrolyte pH from the

353 initial condition to 2.4. However, as shown in Fig. S11, no potential variation was
354 observed between the two pH conditions. This indicates that the participation of H^+ ions
355 is not critical for the conversion reactions or that local solution is buffered, as discussed
356 below.

357 SEM coupled with EDS analyses were conducted on different electrode samples
358 containing the organic materials (PZ, PCA, POH, and PCN) after a full charge (1.4 V vs.
359 Zn/Zn^{2+}) and discharge (0.3 V vs. Zn/Zn^{2+}) at 200 mA g^{-1} (2nd cycle) using 2 mol L^{-1}
360 $ZnSO_4$. As shown in Fig. 4a, the micrographs obtained after the galvanostatic discharge
361 step reveal the formation of plates on a globular carbon matrix. Conversely, the
362 micrographs obtained after the charge step show that these compounds were nearly
363 dissolved. This demonstrates the reversibility of the electrochemical and chemical
364 reactions involved in the process. It is important to note that the formation of the plate-
365 shaped structures did not result in the passivation of the electrode surface (as evidenced
366 by the stability of the tests in Fig. 3), which could have compromised the performance of
367 the device. Similar results were obtained in the study conducted by Vallayil et al. [20];
368 however, these characteristics do not appear to be related to phase transformation. As
369 discussed in the work of Tie et al. [32], the plate-like morphology result from the
370 formation of $Zn_4SO_4(OH)_6 \cdot 4H_2O$ precipitates. Analysis of the EDS spectra obtained from
371 the same micrographs as in Fig. 4a revealed a significant increase in Zn, S and O elements
372 during the discharge step, and conversely, a decrease after the charge step (see Fig. 4b).
373 The evolution of atomic percentages aligns with the appearance and disappearance of
374 plate-shaped structures, likely with a $Zn_4SO_4(OH)_6 \cdot 4H_2O$ stoichiometry. The expected
375 Zn to S atomic ratio of 4:1 was approximately achieved only for PZ (3.4:1). For the
376 remaining active materials, the ratios were 1.6:1, 5.0:1 and 2.6:1 for PCA, POH and PCN,
377 respectively. For comparison purposes, SE micrographs of the PZ compound using
378 $Zn(OTf)_2$ and $Zn(OTf)_2/PVA$ were analyzed, as shown in Fig. S12. The initial globular
379 structure clearly transformed into a homogeneous structure, especially after the discharge
380 step, without the formation of plate-like structures. Additionally, no significant changes
381 were observed after the charge step. The EDS spectra quantification (see Table S2)
382 exhibited a pronounced enrichment in O, F, and S species after the discharge and charge
383 steps, along with high levels of Zn during the discharge process, compared to the as-
384 prepared sample. This behavior suggests that an adherent solid electrolyte interface (SEI)
385 was formed, as discussed below.

386 High-resolution N 1s, O 1s, and Zn 2p_{2/3} spectra were also recorded on samples
387 previously analyzed by SEM. For the N 1s spectra (see Fig. S13), binding energy was
388 largely unaffected between the galvanostatic charge and discharge cycles. For the PZ, a
389 slight shift in the binding energy related to pyridine and N-C was observed from the
390 charge (398.9 and 400.0 eV, respectively) to the discharge (399.3 and 400.5 eV,
391 respectively) process. Additionally, a peak at 401.5 eV has been attributed to quaternary
392 nitrogen. For the PCA and PCN compounds an intense signal of N-O bonds emerged after
393 discharge at 402.5 eV. The observed correlation between the appearance of this peak and
394 the simultaneous decrease of the pyridine signal (399.2 eV) suggests a specific interaction
395 between the pyridine nitrogen (N_β atom) and oxygen of precipitated zinc.

396 During the discharge step, Zn ions are predicted to pair near the N_β atom or close
397 to the substituent groups of the PZ, PCA, POH, and PCN, as predicted by quantum
398 calculations and in agreement with previous study [33]. This occurs specifically at -
399 COOH and -CONH₂ sites, see Fig S14 and Table 2 for the calculated positions and the
400 interaction energy values, respectively. This Zn²⁺ ion pairing could lead to the shift in
401 binding energy observed only for PZ. For PCA, the electron-withdrawing nature of -
402 COOH might reduce the electron density on the PZ ring, potentially making it a weaker
403 Lewis base. This might apply to PCN, but to a lower extent. However, the negative ΔE
404 value for PCA-R (Zn²⁺ ion pairing on the -COOH group) suggests that binding at this
405 specific site is energetically favorable (note the positive values of ΔE for POH and PCN).
406 This could be due to direct coordination of the carboxylate oxygen to Zn²⁺ or other
407 specific interactions. Such behavior could explain the low specific capacity values
408 observed for PCA (see Fig. 3) and the high diffusion coefficient (Fig. S9).

409 In the case of O 1s (see Fig. S15), the observed surface termination groups were
410 similar to those of C 1s (not shown) without a discernible pattern. A minor energy shift
411 of peaks related to O-H, O-C, and O-C=O groups was detected during discharge for the
412 PZ, PCA, and POH compounds. The presence of O-Zn bonds at about 531 eV and its
413 increase after the discharge step (except for PCN) indicate surface precipitation
414 containing Zn. This finding is in agreement with the analysis of Zn 2p_{3/2} spectra (see Fig.
415 S16), where the observed signals were attributed to Zn-O (1022.5 eV) and Zn-SO₄
416 (1023.5) with a small shift to low energy observed for the POH and PZ. The increase in
417 the -OH peak at 531.9 eV may be due to the interaction between Zn-O and the nitrogen
418 of pyridine (Zn-O-N). Strong signal intensities during discharge suggest surface

419 enrichment with Zn, likely due to salt precipitates. The predicted interaction between the
420 carboxylic acid termination on PCA and Zn^{2+} ion was not observed.

421 To gather further evidence on the chemical reactions and charge pairing during
422 charge and discharge cycles, *ex situ* FTIR tests were conducted on electrodes without
423 KCB. For each organic compound, experiments were conducted in ZnSO_4 , as shown in
424 Fig. 5 and Figs. S17 and S18) and, comparatively, $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ (Fig. 6 and Figs. S19 and
425 S20). Detailed information on the mass ratio between active material and KBr, as well as
426 the specific capacitance for each experiment, can be found in Table S3 and Table S4 for
427 ZnSO_4 and $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$, respectively. In the case of the PZ compound and using ZnSO_4 2
428 mol L^{-1} as electrolyte (Fig. 5a), a decrease in the intensity of bands attributed to C-H
429 deformation (from 800 to 600 cm^{-1}) and C-N stretching (from 1200 to 1100 cm^{-1}) of the
430 aromatic ring can be observed during discharge compared to the charge process. In
431 addition, a total conversion of approximately 30% (ratio between specific capacitance
432 obtained during discharge and theoretical capacity) was observed. These findings suggest
433 the occurrence of ion pairing near the aromatic ring or local precipitation of a Zn salt. For
434 the remaining organic compounds, including repeated trials with PZ, the observed bands
435 in the infrared spectra exhibited either an increase or no variation in intensity during the
436 discharge cycle, unlike PZ. In the case of PCA (see Fig. S17, *ca.* 7% conversion), an
437 increase in the intensity of bands attributed to C=O deformation (1736 cm^{-1}) of the
438 carboxylic group and C=C vibrations (especially at 1464 cm^{-1}), C-N stretching (1200 to
439 1100 cm^{-1}), and C-H deformation (800 to 600 cm^{-1}) of the aromatic ring was noticed. For
440 POH (see Fig. 5b, *ca.* 18% conversion), a similar increase in the intensity of bands
441 attributed to C=C vibrations (mainly at 1464 cm^{-1}) and C-N stretching (1200 to 1100 cm^{-1})
442 of the aromatic ring was observed. Finally, for PCN (see Fig. S18, *ca.* 13% conversion),
443 almost no changes were observed in the FTIR spectra, including N-H deformation
444 vibration of the amino group (3400 to 3100 cm^{-1}), except for the C-N band stretching
445 (1200 to 1100 cm^{-1}) of the aromatic ring.

446 All reported data might suggest that ion pairing (Zn^{2+} or H^+) occurs during the
447 initial discharge step. However, as the potential decreases and reaches the cutoff value
448 (0.3 V vs. Zn/Zn^{2+}), the local pH increases to high values, leading to Zn ion precipitation
449 (Fig. 4a). In an interesting work by Passerini *et al.* [34], *operando* pH was measured and
450 exhibited slightly variations during the first charge (3.2 to 4.4) and discharge (4.4 to 4.0)
451 steps using V_2O_5 as cathode. Li *et al.* [33] developed a device to measure the *in situ* pH
452 of a Zn-ion battery containing hexaazatrinaphthalene-phenazine as organic cathode. In

453 the discharge step, the pH rapidly rises from 3.3 (0.8 V) to 5.5 (0.65 V) remaining at that
454 value until 0 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺. Such behavior suggests that H⁺ ions pair with the organic
455 compound during the process. During the FTIR experiments, color changes from yellow
456 to dark red were observed on the electrodes containing POH (without KCB) as the active
457 material (Fig. 5c). POH has two pK_a values, *ca.* 2 and 6.7 for the N in the aromatic ring
458 and hydroxyl substituent, respectively, as predicted using the tool developed in the work
459 of Pan et al. [35]. Therefore, this compound can serve as a local pH probe due to its
460 continuous color change with pH variations. Figure S21 shows the color evolution of a
461 buffered POH solution. Upon analyzing that image, local pH during charge and discharge
462 can reach values lower than 2 (local acidification due to H₂O oxidation) and higher than
463 10 (local alkalization due to O₂/H₂O reduction [36]), respectively. Thus, the attenuation
464 or lack of intensity variation observed during *ex situ* FTIR might be attributed to Zn salt
465 precipitation induced by local alkalization.

466 *Ex situ* FTIR using Zn(OTf)₂ as the electrolyte were also conducted, yielding
467 similar results (see Fig 6a and 6b), *i.e.*, almost no infrared attenuation was observed
468 during the discharge process. However, for all organic compounds investigated, bands
469 attributed to SO₂ symmetric/asymmetric deformation (1200 to 1300 cm⁻¹) and S=O
470 deformation (*ca.* 1035 cm⁻¹) were observed during both the charge and discharge step.
471 Once again, this might suggest the formation of a solid electrolyte interface (SEI), without
472 evidence of Zn²⁺ ion pairing. The appearance of C-F and S=O
473 (symmetrical/asymmetrical) groups were also observed in the work of Shi et al. [37] using
474 Zn(OTf)₂ as electrolyte and was attributed to a (Zn_x(CF₃SO₃)_y(OH)_{2x-y}·nH₂O) byproduct.
475 As previously discussed for ZnSO₄, local alkalization during discharge and
476 acidification during charge were also observed with Zn(OTf)₂ as electrolyte. This is also
477 in agreement with previous papers [38–40]. These pH changes induced corresponding
478 color changes in POH when used as the active material, as shown in Fig 6c for the current
479 collectors and glass fibers. For comparison purposes, Fig S22 shows the images using
480 Zn(OTf)₂/PVA as electrolyte. However, as observed after the charge and discharge step,
481 the resulting SEI appears to remain unaffected by fluctuations in local pH. This is a
482 noteworthy result, as the formation of a SEI is well-established for Zn anode, particularly
483 when using fluorine-rich additives [41]. For instance, in an intriguing work, Chen *et al.*
484 [42] used 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium trifluoromethanesulfonate ([BMIM]OTF) as an
485 additive in a 3 mol L⁻¹ Zn(OTf)₂ electrolyte. This resulted in the formation of a protective
486 SEI layer composed of F, S and Zn salts on the Zn electrode, leading to improved charge

487 transfer kinetics. On the other hand, Barathi *et al.* [43] demonstrated reversible Zn^{2+} ion
488 storage in quinhydrone, involving partial coordination with its carbonyl and hydroxyl
489 groups, as evidenced by shifts in the FTIR spectra. In their study, quinhydrone was used
490 as the organic cathode with a 3 mol L^{-1} $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ electrolyte, and no surface precipitation
491 was observed.

492 Consequently, the use of $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ facilitated the formation of a protective layer
493 on the investigated phenazines, potentially helping to prevent dissolution. That could also
494 be the reason for the proximity of the specific capacity values of phenazines in Fig. 3b.
495 Predicted vibrational spectra of assessed phenazines differed considerably from
496 experimental results (see Fig. S23-S26), mainly due to chemical reactions on cathode
497 surfaces.

498

499 **3.3 Examining the negative electrode using various electrolytes**

500 The electrochemical behavior of Zn in ZnSO_4 , $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$, and $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2/\text{PVA}$
501 electrolytes were assessed through different techniques. During CV, similar oxidation and
502 reduction bands were observed for the ZnSO_4 and $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ electrolytes, as illustrated in
503 Fig. S27. However, when using $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2/\text{PVA}$, a characteristic resistive profile emerged,
504 with the oxidation and reduction bands shifting to higher and lower potentials,
505 respectively. This behavior is expected due to the low concentration of dissolved
506 $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ and the presence of PVA, as evidenced by the higher potential of up to 200 mV
507 difference between the oxidation and reduction plateaus during the stripping and plating
508 experiment (Fig. S28). In the latter, a short circuit occurred around 750 h when ZnSO_4
509 was used as electrolyte, whereas no damage was observed in the Zn/Zn cell until 1370 h
510 with the $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2/\text{PVA}$ electrolytes. As expected, the only deviation was
511 the greater potential difference with PVA. Linear sweep polarization measurements (Fig.
512 S29) indicate Zn has a slightly lower corrosion potential in ZnSO_4 than in $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$, with
513 or without PVA. Additionally, using $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ or $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2/\text{PVA}$ results in a corrosion
514 current two orders of magnitude lower than ZnSO_4 (Table S5). All these results confirm
515 that $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ is the optimal choice for use in ZIB, as it prevents short circuits and enables
516 the formation of a SEI that protects organic active materials without compromising their
517 performance.

518

519 **4. Conclusions**

520

521 The utilization of phenazine, phenazine-1-ol, and phenazine-1-carboxamide as organic
522 cathodes for Zn-ion battery has been successfully evaluated, demonstrating high specific
523 capacitance without dissolution or degradation over graphite substrates, even when using
524 1 A g^{-1} . In contrast, phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA) exhibited suboptimal specific
525 capacity, likely due to the high interaction between the -COOH group and Zn^{2+} ion, as
526 predicted by quantum calculations. The oxidation and reduction peaks of distinct
527 phenazines shifted consistently according to the nature of substituents, in agreement with
528 theoretical predictions. Nonetheless, the biosynthesis of such biomolecule remains
529 feasible and deserves further exploration in the near future. Phenazine-1-ol was proved to
530 be an efficient *in situ* probe for monitoring local pH variations. Notably, the significant
531 alkalinization of the cathode interface during discharge induced surface precipitation
532 when using ZnSO_4 as the electrolyte without passivation. Conversely, the presence of
533 $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ facilitated the formation of a solid electrolyte interface on the phenazines,
534 potentially preventing further dissolution. Such surface modifications, induced by a local
535 rise in pH, resulted in inconclusive *ex situ* FTIR data regarding peak attenuation
536 associated with $\text{Zn}^{2+}/\text{H}^+$ ion pairing. Finally, the incorporation of $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ enhanced the
537 performance and lifetime of the Zn anode during stripping and plate tests.

538

539 **Acknowledgements**

540

541 Financial support and scholarships from the Brazilian funding agencies: São Paulo
542 Research Foundation – FAPESP (#2017/18416-0, #2020/10128-8, and #2024/10909-0),
543 National Council for Scientific and Technological Development – CNPq (#305943/2020-
544 0 and #310055/2023-7), and Coordination of Superior Level Staff Improvement – Capes
545 (Finance Code 001) are gratefully acknowledged. The authors also thank the Laboratory
546 of Structural Characterization (LCE/DEMa/UFSCar) and LNNano/CNPEM for the
547 general facilities and use of XPS (proposal #XPS-20230048), respectively.

548

549 **References**

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- 551 [1] P. Poizot, J. Gaubicher, S. Renault, L. Dubois, Y. Liang, Y. Yao, Opportunities and
552 challenges for organic electrodes in electrochemical energy storage, *Chem. Rev.*
553 120 (2020) 6490–6557. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.9b00482>.
554 [2] G.-Z. Yang, J. Bellingham, P.E. Dupont, P. Fischer, L. Floridi, R. Full, N.
555 Jacobstein, V. Kumar, M. McNutt, R. Merrifield, B.J. Nelson, B. Scassellati, M.

- 556 Taddeo, R. Taylor, M. Veloso, Z.L. Wang, R. Wood, The grand challenges of
557 *Science Robotics*, *Sci. Robot.* 3 (2018) eaar7650.
558 <https://doi.org/10.1126/scirobotics.aar7650>.
- 559 [3] C.-X. Zu, H. Li, Thermodynamic analysis on energy densities of batteries, *Energy*
560 *Environ. Sci.* 4 (2011) 2614. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c0ee00777c>.
- 561 [4] A. Mayyas, D. Steward, M. Mann, The case for recycling: overview and challenges
562 in the material supply chain for automotive li-ion batteries, *Sustainable Mater.*
563 *Technol.* 19 (2019) e00087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susmat.2018.e00087>.
- 564 [5] M.G. Fikru, N. Kilinc-Ata, F. Belaid, Climate policy stringency and trade in energy
565 transition minerals: an analysis of response patterns, *Resour. Policy* 96 (2024)
566 105236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2024.105236>.
- 567 [6] S.S. Parker, M.J. Clifford, B.S. Cohen, Potential impacts of proposed lithium
568 extraction on biodiversity and conservation in the contiguous United States, *Sci.*
569 *Total Environ.* 911 (2024) 168639. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.168639>.
- 570 [7] E. Fan, L. Li, Z. Wang, J. Lin, Y. Huang, Y. Yao, R. Chen, F. Wu, Sustainable
571 recycling technology for Li-ion batteries and beyond: challenges and future
572 prospects, *Chem. Rev.* 120 (2020) 7020–7063.
573 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.9b00535>.
- 574 [8] Y. Liang, H. Dong, D. Aurbach, Y. Yao, Current status and future directions of
575 multivalent metal-ion batteries, *Nat. Energy* 5 (2020) 646–656.
576 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-020-0655-0>.
- 577 [9] T. Ramachandran, R.K. Raji, M. Rezeq, From lab to market: the future of zinc–air
578 batteries powered by MOF/MXene hybrids, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 13 (2025) 12855–
579 12890. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D5TA01344E>.
- 580 [10] Q. Guo, H. Xu, X. Chu, X. Huang, M. Yu, X. Feng, Structural codes of organic
581 electrode materials for rechargeable multivalent metal batteries, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 54
582 (2025) 4035–4086. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4CS01072H>.
- 583 [11] C. Ye, X. Zhou, S. Tang, An azo polymer with abundant active sites and
584 extended conjugation as a stable cathode for high-performance zinc-organic
585 batteries, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 64 (2025) e202501743.
586 <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202501743>.
- 587 [12] Z. Li, J. Tan, Y. Wang, C. Gao, Y. Wang, M. Ye, J. Shen, Building better
588 aqueous Zn-organic batteries, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 16 (2023) 2398–2431.
589 <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3EE00211J>.
- 590 [13] Y. Shi, Y. Yang, L. Li, A review of the advances and prospects of aqueous zinc-
591 based dual-ion batteries, *J. Energy Storage* 136 (2025) 118393.
592 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.118393>.
- 593 [14] Q. Zhao, W. Huang, Z. Luo, L. Liu, Y. Lu, Y. Li, L. Li, J. Hu, H. Ma, J. Chen,
594 High-capacity aqueous zinc batteries using sustainable quinone electrodes, *Sci.*
595 *Adv.* 4 (2018) eaao1761. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aao1761>.
- 596 [15] C. Liedel, Sustainable battery materials from biomass, *ChemSusChem* 13 (2020)
597 2110–2141. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201903577>.
- 598 [16] R. Tang, Y. Feng, Y. Liu, Y. Wu, Q. Liu, G. Hu, X. Liu, Recent advancements
599 of biomass materials in aqueous zinc-ion batteries, *Chem. Eng. J.* 523 (2025)
600 168559. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.168559>.
- 601 [17] L.S. Pierson, E.A. Pierson, Metabolism and function of phenazines in bacteria:
602 impacts on the behavior of bacteria in the environment and biotechnological
603 processes, *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 86 (2010) 1659–1670.
604 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-010-2509-3>.

- 605 [18] Q. Wang, Y. Liu, P. Chen, Phenazine-based organic cathode for aqueous zinc
606 secondary batteries, *J. Power Sources* 468 (2020) 228401.
607 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2020.228401>.
- 608 [19] L. Li, L. Chen, Y. Wen, T. Xiong, H. Xu, W. Zhang, G. Cao, Y. Yang, L. Mai,
609 H. Zhang, Phenazine anodes for ultralongcycle-life aqueous rechargeable batteries,
610 *J. Mater. Chem. A* 8 (2020) 26013–26022. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0TA08600B>.
- 611 [20] P. Vallayil, V.S. Padalkar, C. Nandi, K. Ramanujam, S. Sankararaman, An
612 engineered electrode of phenazine with suitable binder and carbon to exhibit
613 excellent energy and power density in an aqueous organic zinc ion battery, *J. Power*
614 *Sources* 597 (2024) 234153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2024.234153>.
- 615 [21] L.E. Blanc, D. Kundu, L.F. Nazar, Scientific challenges for the implementation
616 of Zn-ion batteries, *Joule* 4 (2020) 771–799.
617 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2020.03.002>.
- 618 [22] W. Yin, K. Hu, F. Wan, R. Liu, W. Chen, Gel electrolyte with excellent zinc-ion
619 conductivity for achieving highly reversible zinc anodes, *ACS Sustainable Chem.*
620 *Eng.* 13 (2025) 14495–14506. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.5c05126>.
- 621 [23] L. Cao, D. Li, E. Hu, J. Xu, T. Deng, L. Ma, Y. Wang, X.-Q. Yang, C. Wang,
622 Solvation structure design for aqueous Zn metal batteries, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 142
623 (2020) 21404–21409. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.0c09794>.
- 624 [24] Y. Luo, C. Li, L. Zhang, X. Tan, Y. Yang, B. Xie, D. Zhang, H. Lang, X. Chen,
625 X. He, Q. Zheng, X. Wu, J. Zhao, B. Xu, D. Lin, Regulating the coordination
626 distance of solvation structure for high-performance aqueous zinc ion batteries,
627 *Chem. Eng. J.* 522 (2025) 168028. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.168028>.
- 628 [25] W. Weppner, R.A. Huggins, Determination of the kinetic parameters of mixed-
629 conducting electrodes and application to the system Li_3Sb , *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 124
630 (1977) 1569–1578. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2133112>.
- 631 [26] C. Lee, W. Yang, R.G. Parr, Development of the Colle-Salvetti correlation-
632 energy formula into a functional of the electron density, *Phys. Rev. B* 37 (1988)
633 785–789. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.37.785>.
- 634 [27] E. Caldeweyher, C. Bannwarth, S. Grimme, Extension of the D3 dispersion
635 coefficient model, *J. Chem. Phys.* 147 (2017) 034112.
636 <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4993215>.
- 637 [28] A. Schäfer, C. Huber, R. Ahlrichs, Fully optimized contracted Gaussian basis
638 sets of triple zeta valence quality for atoms Li to Kr, *J. Chem. Phys.* 100 (1994)
639 5829–5835. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.467146>.
- 640 [29] R. Ahlrichs, M. Bär, M. Häser, H. Horn, C. Kölmel, Electronic structure
641 calculations on workstation computers: The program system turbomole, *Chem.*
642 *Phys. Lett.* 162 (1989) 165–169. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614\(89\)85118-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2614(89)85118-8).
- 643 [30] Z. Lin, L. Lin, J. Zhu, W. Wu, X. Yang, X. Sun, An anti-aromatic covalent
644 organic framework cathode with dual-redox centers for rechargeable aqueous zinc
645 batteries, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 14 (2022) 38689–38695.
646 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaami.2c08170>.
- 647 [31] W. Sun, F. Wang, S. Hou, C. Yang, X. Fan, Z. Ma, T. Gao, F. Han, R. Hu, M.
648 Zhu, C. Wang, Zn/MnO₂ battery chemistry with H⁺ and Zn²⁺ coininsertion, *J. Am.*
649 *Chem. Soc.* 139 (2017) 9775–9778. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.7b04471>.
- 650 [32] Z. Tie, L. Liu, S. Deng, D. Zhao, Z. Niu, Proton insertion chemistry of a zinc–
651 organic battery, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 59 (2020) 4920–4924.
652 <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201916529>.
- 653 [33] S. Li, J. Shang, M. Li, M. Xu, F. Zeng, H. Yin, Y. Tang, C. Han, H. Cheng,
654 Design and synthesis of a π -conjugated N-heteroaromatic material for aqueous

- 655 zinc–organic batteries with ultrahigh rate and extremely long life, *Adv. Mater.* 35
656 (2023) 2207115. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202207115>.
- 657 [34] X. Liu, H. Euchner, M. Zarrabeitia, X. Gao, G.A. Elia, A. Groß, S. Passerini,
658 *Operando* pH Measurements decipher H^+/Zn^{2+} intercalation chemistry in high-
659 performance aqueous $Zn/\delta-V_2O_5$ batteries, *ACS Energy Lett.* 5 (2020) 2979–2986.
660 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.0c01767>.
- 661 [35] X. Pan, H. Wang, C. Li, J.Z.H. Zhang, C. Ji, MolGpka: a web server for small
662 molecule pK_a prediction using a graph-convolutional neural network, *J. Chem. Inf.*
663 *Model.* 61 (2021) 3159–3165. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.1c00075>.
- 664 [36] D. Kundu, S. Hosseini Vajargah, L. Wan, B. Adams, D. Prendergast, L.F. Nazar,
665 Aqueous vs. nonaqueous Zn-ion batteries: consequences of the desolvation penalty
666 at the interface, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 11 (2018) 881–892.
667 <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EE00378E>.
- 668 [37] J. Shi, T. Sun, J. Bao, S. Zheng, H. Du, L. Li, X. Yuan, T. Ma, Z. Tao, “Water-
669 in-deep eutectic solvent” electrolytes for high-performance aqueous Zn-Ion
670 batteries, *Adv. Funct. Materials* 31 (2021) 2102035.
671 <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202102035>.
- 672 [38] F. Wan, S. Huang, H. Cao, Z. Niu, Freestanding potassium vanadate/carbon
673 nanotube films for ultralong-life aqueous zinc-ion batteries, *ACS Nano* 14 (2020)
674 6752–6760. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.9b10214>.
- 675 [39] S. Sariyer, N.M. Keppetipola, O. Sel, R. Demir-Cakan, Microwave-assisted
676 rapid hydrothermal synthesis of vanadium-based cathode: unravelling charge
677 storage mechanisms in aqueous zinc-ion batteries, *ChemSusChem* (2025)
678 e202402445. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.202402445>.
- 679 [40] W. Leng, X. Liu, Y. Gong, Chromium vanadate with unsaturated coordination
680 sites for high-performance zinc-ion battery, *Chem. Eng. J.* 431 (2022) 134034.
681 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.134034>.
- 682 [41] Y. Wang, Z. Wang, F. Yang, S. Liu, S. Zhang, J. Mao, Z. Guo, Electrolyte
683 engineering enables high performance zinc-ion batteries, *Small* 18 (2022) 2107033.
684 <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202107033>.
- 685 [42] J. Chen, W. Zhou, Y. Quan, B. Liu, M. Yang, M. Chen, X. Han, X. Xu, P.
686 Zhang, S. Shi, Ionic liquid additive enabling anti-freezing aqueous electrolyte and
687 dendrite-free Zn metal electrode with organic/inorganic hybrid solid electrolyte
688 interphase layer, *Energy Storage Mater.* 53 (2022) 629–637.
689 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2022.10.004>.
- 690 [43] P. Barathi, P. Vinothbabu, S. Sampath, Use of quinhydrone as a promising
691 cathode material for aqueous zinc-ion battery, *J. Energy Storage* 74 (2023) 109154.
692 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2023.109154>.
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Tables

695

696

697 **Table 1** Values of “ x ” obtained from the assessment of the relationship between scan rate
698 and mass current density, alongside the peak potentials of the anodic and cathodic
699 processes.

Active material	x_{anodic}	$E_{\text{anodic}} / \text{V}$	x_{cathodic}	$E_{\text{cathodic}} / \text{V}$
PZ	0.502 ± 0.007	0.767 ± 0.007	0.52 ± 0.02	0.614 ± 0.005
PCA	0.54 ± 0.04	0.88 ± 0.02	0.56 ± 0.03	0.73 ± 0.02
POH	0.611 ± 0.002	0.703 ± 0.001	0.581 ± 0.003	0.560 ± 0.002
PCN	0.589 ± 0.002	0.798 ± 0.009	0.63 ± 0.02	0.699 ± 0.006

700

701

702 **Table 2** HOMO (E_{HOMO}), LUMO (E_{LUMO}), HOMO-LUMO gap (H-L gap), Fermi, and Interaction energies (ΔE) between phenazine derivatives
 703 and Zn^{2+}

Systems	Zn^{2+} position	$E_{\text{HOMO}} / \text{eV}$	$E_{\text{LUMO}} / \text{eV}$	HOMO-LUMO gap ($ E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}} $)	Fermi level ($(E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_{\text{LUMO}})/2$)	$\Delta E / \text{eV}$
PZ		-6.31	-2.67	3.64	-4.49	---
PZ	N_β or N_τ	-14.26	-13.18	1.08	-13.72	0.00
POH*	---	-5.98	-2.75	3.23	-4.37	---
POH	N_β	-13.85	-12.77	1.08	-13.31	0.00
POH	N_τ	-13.81	-12.81	1.00	-13.31	0.56
PCA	---	-6.86	-3.35	3.51	-5.11	---
PCA	N_β	-14.04	-12.18	1.86	-13.11	0.00
PCA	N_τ	-14.30	-13.49	0.81	-13.90	1.64
PCA	R	-13.45	-12.60	0.85	-13.03	-0.63
PCN	---	-6.59	-3.06	3.54	-4.83	---
PCN	N_β	-13.862	-11.80	2.06	-12.83	0.00
PCN	N_τ	-13.92	-13.16	0.75	-13.54	1.54
PCN	R	-13.12	-12.48	0.64	-12.80	0.78

704 *Note: No stable positions for the Zn^{2+} ion were found near the OH group.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

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Fig. 1 Cyclic voltammograms (2nd cycle at 0.1 mV s^{-1}) of electrodes synthesized with phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), 1-hydroxiphenazine (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) and containing the Ketjen Carbon Black (KCB) conductive carbon material (20% *m/m*) and PVDF (15% *m/m*). The gray region indicates the response of only the KCB carbon material (prepared with 85% *m/m* and 15% *m/m* PVDF). **Conditions:** A Zn foil was used as the anode and $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ served as the electrolyte. The arrows indicate the direction of the applied potential scan rate.

Fig. 2 Specific capacity of the discharge cycle (*C*) using different organic materials as active materials (refer to the numbers in pink in the inset, which are measured in mA g^{-1}) as a function of the number of cycles during the galvanostatic charging and discharging tests at different mass current densities (indicated at the top of the figure). **Conditions:** A Zn foil was used as the anode and $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ served as the electrolyte. Phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), 1-hydroxiphenazine (POH), phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN), and Ketjen carbon black (KCB: 85% *m/m* with PVDF 15% *m/m*).

Fig. 3 Specific capacity of the discharge cycle (*C*) as a function of the number of cycles during galvanostatic charge and discharge tests at 1 A g^{-1} using **a)** $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ and **b)** $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ Zn(OTf)}_2$ as electrolytes. For each active material, two different experiments were carried out, with colors referring to the different materials used. Prior to these tests, the active material was analyzed by EI and activated through cyclic voltammetry (5 cycles at 0.5 mV s^{-1}). **Conditions:** Zn as anode. Phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), 1-hydroxiphenazine (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN).

Fig. 4 a) Scanning electron micrographs and **b)** atomic percentage obtained from EDS spectra of electrode materials containing phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), 1-hydroxiphenazine (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) as active material and after the charge ($1.4 \text{ vs. Zn/Zn}^{2+}$) and discharge steps ($0.3 \text{ vs. Zn/Zn}^{2+}$) using $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ as electrolyte. The working electrodes were prepared with Ketjen carbon black and PVDF. Separate electrodes were prepared for each half cycle and using a Zn foil as anode.

740 **Fig 5** *Ex situ* Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of the **a**) phenazine (PZ) and **b**)
741 phenazine-1-ol (POH) compound after use as the active material in the cathode of a Zn-
742 ion battery under different conditions: pristine, after the charge step (1.3 V), and after the
743 discharge step (0.3 V) using 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte. **c**) Image of electrodes
744 prepared with phenazine-1-ol (POH) as active material and PVDF as binder: *i*) after
745 discharge step until 0.3 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺, *ii*) as prepared electrode, and *iii*) after the charge
746 step until 1.4 V vs Zn/Zn²⁺ using 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte. Experimental
747 conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution
748 in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB.

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750 **Fig. 6** *Ex situ* Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of the **a**) phenazine (PZ) and **b**)
751 phenazine-1-ol (POH) compound after use as the active material in the cathode of a Zn-
752 ion battery under different conditions: pristine, after the charge step (1.4 V), and after the
753 discharge step (0.3 V) using 2 mol L⁻¹ Zn(OTf)₂ as electrolyte. **c**) Image of electrodes
754 prepared with phenazine-1-ol (POH) as active material and PVDF as binder: *i*) after the
755 charge step until 1.4 V vs Zn/Zn²⁺ and after discharge step until 0.3 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺ and **d**)
756 image of the glass fibers after the charge (*iii*) and discharge (*iv*) steps using 2 mol L⁻¹
757 Zn(OTf)₂ as electrolyte. Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared
758 with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB.